

Macrocyclic complexes : Synthesis and characterization of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with [14]1,4,5,7,8,11,12,14-octaaza-2,3,9,10-tetraoxo-1,4,5,6,6,7,8,11,12,13,13,14-dodecahydrocyclotetradecane (OTCT)

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Abstract : A series of macrocyclic complexes of the titled ligand have been isolated by the action of formaldehyde (H₂CO) on bis-(1,4-diamino-1,4-diaza-2,3-dioxobutane) complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II). The coordination template effect governs the steric course of the reaction. The structures of the complexes have been elucidated on the basis of IR, electronic, ESR spectral data, magnetic properties, electrochemical studies and thermal data. Electrochemical studies show that all the complexes show two well defined reduction curves corresponding to the formation of species where the metal ion can be formally assigned an oxidation state of +I and zero respectively.

Keywords : Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, macrocyclic complex, synthesis, OTCT.

Introduction

Vicinal amino groups (-NH₂) in the metal complexes of dihydrazides and dihydrazones¹⁻³ have been used as intermediates to prepare macrocyclic clathrochelate complexes of transition metals by the template reaction with aldehydes and ketones^{4,5}. However, cyclisation of these precursor molecules (hydrazide/hydrazone complexes) involving the vicinal amino groups with formaldehyde is least studied. In continuation of our earlier work⁶⁻⁹, we report the synthesis and characterization of a series of 14-membered octaaza, 5 : 6 : 5 : 6 annulated macrocyclic complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metals.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of Galaxo/E. Merck grade. Solvents and metal salts were used without further purification. All the complexes were prepared by the method as described for the preparation of [Ni(OTCT)(H₂O)₂]Cl₂ complex as follows :

The precursor complex¹⁰ bis-(1,4-diamino-1,4-diaza-2,3-dioxobutane)nickel(II) chloride (0.4 g; 1 mmol) was suspended in 30-50 ml of acetonitrile maintaining the

temperature at 40 °C. It was treated with (1.8 g; 2 mmol) aqueous formaldehyde (37%). Care was taken for the drop wise addition of formaldehyde with continuous and vigorous stirring, because bulk addition of it resulted in a gummy product with unknown composition. After about 30-40 min, the solids passed in to solutions with a change in colors from blue to light brown. The resulting solution is reduced to half its volume after stirring for 2 h. The concentrated solution is filtered and treated with a chilled solution of *n*-butanol and ether (1 : 1). A light brown crystalline product is isolated. It is filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum.

The metal contents of all complexes were estimated by standard methods^{11,12}. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated with a MLW-CHN micro analyzer. The reflectance and IR spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Carry 2390 and Perkin-Elmer 389 spectrophotometer respectively. The ESR spectra of copper(II) complexes were recorded as powder samples (polycrystalline) on an E-112 EPR spectrometer with field set at 3200G, scan range, 2.0XI KG, modulation frequency 9.44 GHz, receiver again

10×10^2 and modulation amplitude $0.63 \times 10G$. The conductivities of the complexes in dioxan/DMF were measured with a Systronics conductivity bridge. The room temperature magnetic moment values were determined by Gouy's method using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as calibrant. Electrochemical studies were made with a Systronics polarograph type 1632 in 80% DMF with $KClO_4$ as the supporting electrolyte.

Results and discussion

The complexes are stable at room temperature having melting points >250 °C. They are feebly attacked by dil. acids and alkalis and their molar conductance values in dioxan/DMF suggest that they are 1 : 2 electrolytes.

Formation of macrocyclic complexes is shown as below :

The formation of 5 : 6 : 5 : 6 annular macrocyclic complexes is confirmed by their analytical data (Table 1) and other physico-chemical studies.

IR spectral studies :

The IR spectra of the macrocycles were compared with those of the precursor and other related complexes. The precursor complexes band undergoes drastic changes upon cyclisation. A peak at ~ 3500 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the combined mode of ν_{OH} , ν_{NH} , ν_{H_2O} . Dis-

appearance of the precursor bands at ~ 1730 cm^{-1} and ~ 1120 cm^{-1} due to NH_2 group and the occurrence of a band due to ν_{C-N} at a comparatively higher frequency region (~ 1600 cm^{-1}) support the ring closure as well as electron transfer from the metal to the ligand via Π network¹³. An increase in the absorption frequency of δ_{NH} at ~ 1255 cm^{-1} and appearance of a strong band at ~ 450 cm^{-1} due to ν_{M-N} also confirm that the ligand is coordinated with the metal ion through imino nitrogen. The bands observed at ~ 760 , ~ 545 and ~ 425 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to $\rho_r H_2O$, $\rho_w H_2O$ mode and ν_{M-O} respectively^{14,15}.

The appearance of ν_{CH_2} and δ_{CH_2} at ~ 2840 and 1150 , 800 cm^{-1} respectively¹⁶ suggests the formation of macrocyclic complexes. Occurrence of a single band at ~ 1600

cm^{-1} instead of a doublet¹⁷ is probably due to bathochromic shift of ν_{C-N} bands arising as a result of the non-involvement of $-CH_2-$ group in tautomerisation.

Since the IR spectra of the complexes indicated presence of coordinated water, thermogravimetric studies were also undertaken to ascertain their nature. In all the cases thermograms of the complexes followed the same pattern of thermal decomposition. The complexes remained almost unaffected upto 130 °C and thereafter a slight

Table 1. Physico-chemical and electrometric data of the complexes

Sl. no.	Formula of the complex (Colour)	Mol. Wt. Calcd. (Found)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					$E(1)_{1/2}$	$E(2)_{1/2}$
			M	C	H	N*	X ¹		
1.	[Co(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ (Orange red)	420 (425)	13.62 (13.65)	16.84 (16.94)	3.57 (3.76)	26.21 (26.35)	16.57 (16.71)	0.32	0.43
2.	[Co(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂]Br ₂ (Deep purple)	504 (514)	10.13 (11.28)	13.97 (14.01)	3.00 (3.11)	21.62 (21.79)	31.02 (31.13)	0.45	0.50
3.	[Co(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Dark brown)	480 (478)	12.27 (12.13)	15.18 (15.06)	3.18 (3.35)	29.12 (29.29)	-	0.53	0.48
4.	[Ni(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	430 (426)	13.74 (13.85)	16.73 (16.90)	3.62 (3.76)	26.17 (26.29)	16.52 (16.67)	0.72	1.32
5.	[Ni(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂]Br ₂	510 (515)	11.37 (11.46)	13.77 (13.98)	3.03 (3.11)	21.54 (21.75)	31.12 (31.07)	0.81	1.39
6.	[Ni(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	480 (479)	12.35 (12.32)	15.18 (15.03)	3.17 (3.34)	29.18 (29.33)	-	0.70	1.41
7.	[Cu(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	422 (431)	14.62 (14.65)	16.56 (16.72)	3.78 (3.72)	26.21 (26.02)	16.35 (16.49)	0.62	1.21
8.	[Cu(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂]Br ₂	507 (520)	12.18 (12.22)	13.72 (13.86)	3.17 (3.08)	21.43 (21.56)	34.54 (34.65)	0.63	1.23
9.	[Cu(OTCT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	478 (484)	12.79 (13.13)	14.74 (14.89)	3.24 (3.30)	28.79 (28.96)	-	0.60	1.19

decomposition upto 180 °C was observed. The weight loss at this temperature range corresponds to loss of two water molecules. The elimination of water molecules at a comparatively higher temperature indicated them to be coordinated which is in conformity with our earlier observation of IR studies. Beyond 350 °C the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage of weight loss which continues upto 450 °C forming the stable oxides.

Electronic spectral data and magnetic properties :

Reflectance spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes show two bands at ~ 8300 cm⁻¹ and 19000 cm⁻¹ indicating that the complexes have an O_h symmetry¹⁸ around them. Ligand field parameters such as 10Dq, B, β etc. are given in Table 2. The room temperature magnetic moment values of the cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.82–4.92 B.M. and are in good agreement with the proposed geometry. Besides the above bands, a highly intense band is observed in the region ~ 25000–26000 cm⁻¹, which is assigned to charge transfer.

Table 2. Electronic and ESR data for the complexes with OTCT

Sl. no.	10Dq	B	β	D _q ^E	D _q ^A	D _t	G ₁	G _⊥	A ₁ × 10 ⁻⁴ (cm ⁻¹)	A _⊥ × 10 ⁻⁴ (cm ⁻¹)	α ²
1.	9301	798	0.815								
2.	9248	790	0.813								
3.	9389	763	0.786								
4.				1251	409	481					
5.				1279	421	613					
6.				1291	389	515					
7.							2.31	2.045	194	104	0.904
8.							2.31	2.042	193	101	0.902
9.							2.30	2.040	192	95	0.887

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) complexes show bands at ~ 8300 , 12510 and 26000 cm^{-1} indicating a *trans*-axial distortion leading to D_{4h} symmetry¹⁹ around the metal center. The tetragonal parameters such as D_t , D_q^E , D_q^A etc. are given in Table 2. The room temperature magnetic moment values of these complexes lie in the range 3.04–3.13 B.M.

The copper(II) complexes possess magnetic moment value of 1.60 B.M. per gram ion of copper(II). A broad asymmetric band at $\sim 16400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. Like the precursor complexes it resembles the feature of the square planar copper(II) complexes under D_{4h} symmetry²⁰. A strong and intense band observed at $\sim 24000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to $M \rightarrow L$ (π) charge transfer transitions.

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectra of the copper(II) complexes exhibit well resolved anisotropic signals in parallel and perpendicular ⁶³Copper region. A representative ESR spectra of the chloro complex is presented in Fig. 1. The magnetic parameters (g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp}), bonding parameters (A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp}) and covalency parameters (α^2) are listed in Table 2. The observation that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$, suggests a major distortion of

copper(II) complexes from O_h symmetry to D_{4h} symmetry^{20a}. The α^2 values show considerable covalent character in bonding involving metal ion and ligand^{21,22}.

Polarographic studies :

The half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) and related polarographic data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The plot of $\log(i_d - i)/i \sim E$ for the reduction of the complex is presented in Fig. 2. The redox behaviour has been determined in 80% DMF medium with sodium perchlorate as the supporting electrolyte at an ionic strength of 0.1 M. The plots of $(i_d - i)/i$ versus E are linear with slope = -1 near 65 mV. The polarograms of the macro-cycles show two redox waves; the $E(1)_{1/2}$ and $E(2)_{1/2}$ lie near -0.72 V and -1.32 V respectively, for nickel(II); -0.62 V and -1.21 V respectively for copper(II). The $E(1)_{1/2}$ and $E(2)_{1/2}$ values of cobalt(II) complexes are almost similar i.e. 0.32 V and 0.43 V respectively. The polarographic electrode processes are diffusion controlled. The diffusion current constant for the complexes suggest the transfer of one electron at each redox step and is further confirmed from the value of I_d and calculated value of 'n', the number of electron transferred by Ilkovic's equation. The $E_{1/2}$ values of both the redox waves for all

Fig. 1. ESR spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{OTCT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: Scan range, $2.1 \times 1 \text{ KG}$; time constant, 0.128 s; modulation amplitude, $0.5 \times 10\text{G}$; receiver gain, 3.2×10^3 ; microwave power, 20 mV; field set, 3200G; scan time, 4 min; modulation frequency, 100 KHz; microwave frequency, 9.36 GHz.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log \left(\frac{i_d - i}{i} \right)$ vs E for the reduction of (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{OTCT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$, (b) $[\text{Ni}(\text{OTCT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Br}_2$ and (c) $[\text{Cu}(\text{OTCT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

the metal ions are more cathodic relative to the previous series of macrocyclic complexes²³ reported earlier. It is

noteworthy that the relative degree of shift of $E_{1/2(2)}$ values for the second step of reduction is higher than that of first waves for almost all the metal complexes.

XRD studies :

The XRD data were analyzed using LSUCRIPC software (Courtesy R Garvey, North Dakota University, USA, through Dr. B. S. Acharya, IMMT, Bhubaneswar) using an IBM compatible PC-AT(80486, 66 MHz).

It has been observed that the unit cell of both nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes are tetragonal and unit cell of cobalt(II) complexes are monoclinic²⁴. The cell edge (a , b , c), the axial angle (α , β , ν) and volume of the unit cell are recorded in Table 3. It is evident from IR spectra that the anions are not involved in structural determination. The structures of the complexes are mainly due to the central metal ion. So the atoms are closely packed in the unit cell in the order : cobalt(II) > nickel(II) \approx copper(II).

Conclusion :

The Structure I has been proposed for the macrocyclic complexes, which will satisfy all our foregoing observations.

where, $M = \text{u}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} \text{ and } \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$;
 $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_3^- \text{ and } \text{SO}_4^{2-}$

Table 3. Structural parameters of the complexes of OTCT as determined by XRD data

Sl. no.	Complex	a	b	c	α	β	ν	Vol. A ⁰³	Crystal class
1.	$[\text{Co}(\text{OTCT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	13.199	13.390	9.180	90°	97.68°	90°	1607	Monoclinic
2.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{OTCT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	9.464	14.730	9.236	90°	90°	90°	1287.60	Tetragonal
3.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{OTCT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	17.497	23.083	8.274	90°	90°	90°	3341.55	Tetragonal

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